

RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF HYPERTROPHIC CARDIOMYOPATHY IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Cardiomyopathies are the most severe diseases in children, they are characterized by cardiac arrhythmias, thromboembolic complications and a frequent fatal outcome in the form of sudden cardiac death. [9]. Our study aimed to evaluate the risk factors for developing hypertrophic cardiomyopathy in children. Materials and methods: 85 children under 18 years of age with cardiomyopathy were examined, of which 60 children had dilated cardiomyopathy (DCMP), 16 children had hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCMP) and 9 children had restrictive cardiomyopathy (RCMP). All children were hospitalized in the cardio-rheumatological department of the Republican Specialized Scientific Practical Medical Center of Pediatrics of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The control group consisted of 30 healthy children.*

Keywords: *children, hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, risk factors, echocardiography.*

Relevance. Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCMP) is a myocardial disease characterized by massive hypertrophy of the left ventricular myocardium not associated with increased pressure loading [1]. HCMP is a frequent form of cardiomyopathies in children arising from gene mutations encoding proteins of the sarcomeric and non-sarcomeric complexes. The causes of HCMP in childhood are diverse [2,3,4,5]. Early diagnosis of metabolic forms of HCMP is of great importance; in some cases, regression of hypertrophy on the background of enzyme replacement or other drug therapy is possible [6]. Hereditary predisposition is considered to be a risk factor for HCMP [7]. HCMP can be combined with different pathologies of a genetic nature.

According to the recommendations of experts of the working group on hypertrophic cardiomyopathy of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC), the US Heart Association [8], HCMP, a hereditary disease, is transmitted by autosomal dominant trait. The genetic defect occurs when a mutation in one of 10 genes, each of which encodes components of cardiac sarcomere protein and determines the development of myocardial hypertrophy. About 200 mutations responsible for the development of the disease have been identified [9]. In addition to genetic aspects, the following factors predispose to the development of HCMP: intrauterine developmental delay; hyperproduction and enhanced action of catecholamines on the myocardium; primary myocardial metabolic disorder; lesion of small intramural vessels of the heart [10,11,12].

Symmetric and asymmetric forms are distinguished depending on the symmetry of cardiac muscle hypertrophy. The main criterion for determining the morphologic variant of hypertrophy is the value of the ratio of LV thickness to the thickness of the posterior LV wall. Their ratio of more than 1.3 is considered as asymmetric HCMP, less than 1.3 - as symmetric HCMP [13,14].

More than half of deaths occur suddenly, which may be the first and only manifestation of the disease. The incidence of sudden death in children is 4-6%. There is no clear relationship between the intraventricular pressure gradient at rest and the occurrence of sudden death. Even an asymptomatic course of HCMP can end in sudden death [14].

Thus, due to the development of high-tech cardiac imaging methods, the diagnosis of HCMP has improved in the last 10 years. This allows early diagnosis and treatment measures aimed at preventing adverse outcomes, including sudden cardiac death.

Our study aimed to research risk factors for developing hypertrophic cardiomyopathy in children.

Materials and methods: We examined 85 children with cardiomyopathy under the age of 18, of which 60 children had dilated cardiomyopathy (DCMP), 16 children with hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCMP) and 9 children with restrictive cardiomyopathy (RCMP) hospitalized in the cardio-rheumatological department of the Republican specialized scientific-practical medical center of pediatrics of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The diagnosis was made based on complaints, anamnesis data (obstetric anamnesis of the mother, anamnesis of the life and illness of the child, previous diseases, the nature of the course and duration of the disease), functional (ECG, echocardiography, Holter ECG monitoring), biochemical (determination of cardio specific markers - creatine kinase, lactate dehydrogenase), immunological (cytokines - tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF), IL-1, IL-6, IL-8,) and instrumental (chest x-ray, chest multispiral computed tomography) research methods.

ECG was performed on patients in a planned manner during each hospitalization in the Department of Cardiorheumatology, both during the initial examination and during re-hospitalization to the department on the ultrasound machine Aplio-500 (Toshiba, Japan) with sector sensors 3.0-6.5 MHz. Echocardiography was performed according to standard methods following local and foreign guidelines and recommendations. Two-dimensional echocardiography with the determination of echometric parameters was used. The contractility of the left ventricular myocardium was assessed by the ejection fraction (EF) by the Teicholtz or Simpson method and the shortening fraction of the left ventricular myocardium (SF) [6].

Results and discussion. Studies on the distribution of cardiomyopathies in the Republic of Karakalpakstan have shown that the genetically determined form of cardiomyopathies HCMP is most often detected in the ecologically unfavorable zone of the Aral Sea region (the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm region) - 56.3%, and in the Republic of Karakalpakstan this indicator amounted to 43.7% (Fig1).

Fig №.1. Distribution of children with cardiomyopathies by place of residence (%)

Analysis of medical and biological factors showed that the disease is associated with sex: DCMP is more common in boys (63.3±6.2%), HCMP and RCMP are more common in girls (75.0±10.8% and 77.7±13.8% respectively). The age of the parents is also important, so in children with HCMP, the age of mothers in 37.5±12.1% of cases at the time of the birth of this child was over 35 years old, in mothers of children with DCMP - in 38.3±6.3%, and in mothers of children with RCMP - in 55.5±16.6% of cases, i.e., severe forms of CMP to a greater extent were due to the age of mothers over 35 years (Fig. 2).

Fig.2. Medical and biological factors in the development of cardiomyopathies in children

Note: a - reliability of differences in indicators between the indicators of children with DCMP and children with HCMP; b-between the indicators of children with DCMP and children with RCMP; c -between the indicators of children with HCMP and RCMP.

This pattern is typical regardless of the region of residence of the examined children. The figure shows the reliability of differences in the determinants of health between the regions where children live.

Statistical analysis shows that in the development of cardiomyopathies, the predominant place belongs to diseases associated with lifestyle (%) and the health of future parents (%) and mothers during pregnancy (%). Studies have shown that one of the medical-biological determinants that has a significant impact on the development of cardiomyopathy is also the burdened obstetric anamnesis of mothers.

We conducted a comparative analysis of maternal risk factors for developing cardiomyopathies. To assess the prognostic unfavorable anamnestic data, the following were considered: the mother's age, the somatic pathology of the pregnant woman, the presence of infectious diseases during pregnancy, and the nature of the course of pregnancy. The state of health of pregnant women was analyzed from the concept of perinatal risk.

As can be seen from Figure 3, in the development of DCMP, the most unfavorable maternal factors during pregnancy were preeclampsia (33.3%), miscarriages in previous pregnancies (20.0%), stillbirths in previous pregnancies (16.6%) and polyhydramnios (16.6%).

Fig. 3. Obstetric history of mothers of children with cardiomyopathies

In the development of HCMP, the leading factors were preeclampsia (37.5%), oligohydramnios (37.5%), preterm birth (31.2%), polyhydramnios (25.0%), miscarriages in previous pregnancies (18.7%) and stillbirths in previous pregnancies (12.5%). In the obstetric history in children with RCMP, oligohydramnios prevailed (33.3%), preeclampsia, polyhydramnios, preterm labor, and stillbirth in previous pregnancies were equally (22.2%) noted; 11.1% had miscarriages in previous pregnancies. As can be seen from these results, the most unfavorable factors in severe forms of CMP are preeclampsia, oligohydramnios, and adverse course and outcomes of previous pregnancies.

Anamnestic data on past diseases and their etiology are essential for the diagnosis and early detection of CMP. As Table 1 shows, viral infections are significant among past diseases for all forms of CMP, and bacterial infections are also substantial for HCMP and RCMP.

Table 1. Past diseases of children with cardiomyopathies

Past illnesses	Children with DCMP (n=60) (%)	Children with HCMP (n=16) (%)	Children with RCMP (n=9) (%)	P	P ₁	P ₂
Acute respiratory viral infection	76,7±5,5	100±0,0	100±0,0	<0,05	<0,05	>0,05
Chicken pox	33,3±6,1	18,8±9,8	22,2±13,9	>0,05	>0,05	>0,05
Bronchopneumonia	18,3±5,0	37,5±12,1	33,3±15,7	>0,05	>0,05	>0,05
Acute intestinal infections	10±3,9	31,25±11,6	44,4±16,6	<0,05	<0,05	>0,05
Purulent tonsillitis	8,3±3,6	25±10,8	33,3±15,7	>0,05	<0,05	>0,05
Pyelonephritis	6,7±3,2	18,75±9,8	-	<0,05	-	-
Non-rheumatic myocarditis	10,0±3,9	18,75±9,8	-	>0,05	-	-
Sepsis	8,3±3,6	12,5±8,2	22,2±13,9	<0,05	<0,05	>0,05
Epid. mumps	-	12,5±8,3	-	-	-	-
Viral hepatitis B	-	-	22,2±13,9	-	-	-
Viral hepatitis A	-	-	11,1±10,5	-	-	-

Note: P - reliability of differences in indicators between the indicators of children with DCMP and children with HCMP; P₁ – between indicators of children with DCMP and children with RCMP; P₂ - between the indicators of children with HCMP and RCMP

The study of indicators of physical development of children with CMP revealed the presence of deviations in indicators of growth, body weight and body mass index relative to age norms. The indicators were evaluated using the WHO Antro and Antro plus software.

The analysis of the obtained results showed that growth delay was detected among patients with CMP - in 13.9% of children, growth rates relative to age were in the range from -3SD to -2SD, corresponding to low growth. Low weight relative to age (indicators ranging from -3SD to -2SD) was determined in 30.2% of children. The most reliable indicator in the harmonious development of children is the body mass index (BMI). According to this indicator, 31.0% of children living in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the Khorezm region have a risk of protein-energy malnutrition (PEM), 24.1% of children have moderate PEM, and 6.8% of children have severe PEM degree (exhaustion). These figures in the aggregate of children living in other regions amounted to 19.2%, 10.5% and 3.5%, respectively.

The physical development of a growing organism is one of the leading indicators of a child's health. The more significant disorders in physical development, the greater the likelihood of disease. In turn, the presence of a chronic pathological process always has a considerable impact on the physical development of children. At the same time, according to the laws, physical development depends on several biomedical and environmental factors, as evidenced by our indicators of the physical development of children, depending on the place of residence.

It is important to note that in children of the Aral Sea region, diseases of the circulatory organs against the background of low physical development were diagnosed 4-6 times more often than in children of Tashkent. At the same time, in every third child, chronic forms of pathology of the circulatory organs were combined with chronic bronchopulmonary diseases, while this combination was not observed in children in Tashkent. Based on complaints, three primary clinical syndromes can be equally distinguished in children with all forms of cardiomyopathy: astheno-vegetative, cardiac, and cardiorespiratory. Among the complaints, the most common were general weakness (93%), shortness of breath (81.4%), and discomfort or pain in the region of the heart (23.2%); the latter was most characteristic of older children.

In the course of this study, a differential diagnostic and correlation analysis of the relationship between the parameters of a biochemical blood test, structural and functional remodeling of the cardiovascular system and the clinical and functional status of children with dilated cardiomyopathy and non-rheumatic myocarditis depending on health determinants was carried out with the calculation of Pearson's correlation coefficients.

Table 2. Correlation relationship between laboratory and functional parameters in children with CMP

Indicators	DCMP			HCMP			RCMP		
	EF <40%	EDS LV	EDV LV	EF >55%	EDS LV	EDV LV	EF >55%	EDS LV	EDV LV
Na+	0,19	-0,45	-0,36	0,02	0,14	0,01	0,01	0,15	0,18
CPK-MB	-0,46	0,38	-0,42	-0,06	0,10	0,13	-0,06	0,13	0,12
ALT (<40)	-0,34	0,25	0,26	0,01	0,00	0,2	0,01	0,00	0,10
AST (<35)	-0,35	0,22	0,19	0,00	0,05	0,13	0,00	0,04	0,14
De Ritis ratio (AST/ALT)	-0,39	-0,23	-0,13	-0,24	-0,05	-0,06	-0,12	-0,04	-0,05
NT-pro BNP	-0,45	0,42	0,45	0,12	-0,11	-0,1	0,12	-0,12	-0,1
HR	-0,39	-0,17	0,38	-0,21	-0,14	0,12	-0,21	-0,24	0,22

An analysis of correlation relationships showed that an increase in the concentration of brain natriuretic peptide (BNP), reflecting the activity of neurohumoral mechanisms of progression of CHF, is associated with an increase in the diameter of the LV EDS ($r = 0.42$; $p < 0.01$), LV EDV ($r = 0.40$; $p < 0.01$) in children with DCMP. LV EF ($r = -0.35$; $p < 0.05$) also significantly decreased with increasing BNP concentration. The concentration of BNP significantly negatively correlated with sodium level in the blood, reflecting ($r = -0.28$) kidney damage typical for patients with CHF. Also, the sodium concentration significantly negatively correlated with the potassium concentration ($r = -0.32$; $p < 0.05$), reflecting multidirectional electrolyte imbalance and indirectly confirming the trend towards an increase in potassium concentration, characteristic of CHF. A negative relationship was found between the sodium concentration and such indicators of the structural and functional restructuring of the heart as the LV EDS diameter ($r = -0.35$; $p < 0.05$), LV EDV ($r = -0.26$).

HR positively correlated with LV EDV diameter ($r = 0.38$; $p < 0.05$) and negatively with LV EF ($r = -0.29$; $p < 0.05$), which confirms the proposition that an increase in heart rate is associated with impaired central hemodynamics and a decrease in the effectiveness of systolic contraction.

Structural and functional parameters of the heart showed close relationships between disorders of LV systolic function, increased pressure in the pulmonary artery and dilatation of the heart cavities.

It was found that the frequency of polyhydramnios positively correlated with LV EDS ($r = 0.42$; $p < 0.01$), LV EDV ($r = 0.32$; $p < 0.05$) in children with HCMP. This relationship indicates a possible illness (idiopathic) transferred during pregnancy. Also, the frequency of preeclampsia during pregnancy was positively correlated with EF ($r = 0.41$; $p < 0.01$) in children with DCMP.

In turn, these indicators are in a strong correlation with such determinants of health as place of residence - an ecologically unfavorable zone of the Aral Sea region ($r = 0.72$; $p < 0.001$), mother's age over 35 years ($r = 0.58$; $p < 0.001$), and in the average correlation relationship with closely related marriage ($r = 0.44$; $p < 0.01$) and heredity ($r = 0.32$; $p < 0.05$).

Table 3 shows the correlation dependence of functional indicators and health determinants. The most reliable echocardiographic parameters of DCMP were selected.

Table 3. Correlation between health determinants and functional indicators in children with CMP

Indicators	DCMP			HCMP			RCMP		
	EF <40%	EDS LV	EDV LV	EF >55%	EDS LV	EDV LV	EF >55%	EDS LV	EDV LV
Aral region	- 0,61	0,72	0,70	-0,24	0,25	0,36	- 0,22	0,12	0,00
Maternal age >35 years	-0,52	0, 53	0,62	-0,16	0,24	0,23	-0,05	0, 22	0,62
Closely related marriage	-0,34	0,46	0,42	-0,19	0,18	0,19	-0,12	0,05	0,00
Heredity	-0,35	0,34	0,32	-0,21	0,15	0,17	-0,05	0,05	0,15
Preeclampsia	- 0,41	0,36	0,47	-0,24	0,24	0,15	- 0,12	0,12	0,14
Polyhydramnios	-0,28	0,24	0,27	-0,18	0,42	0,32	-0,15	0,01	0,15

As can be seen from Table 3., in children with DCMP, strong correlations ($p < 0.001$) of such EchoCG indicators as LV EDS and LV ECV with the indicators of children living in the Aral Sea

region were revealed ($r = 0.64$ and $r = 0.72$ - respectively) and a strong negative relationship with EF <40% ($r = -0.61$), as well as average correlations ($p < 0.01$) with maternal age, closely related marriage and preeclampsia, a weak correlation ($p < 0.05$) with heredity. In children with HCMP, only the LV EDV indicator was significantly associated with the Aral Sea region ($r = 0.36$; $p < 0.01$).

Table 4. Correlation between health determinants and laboratory parameters in children with CMP

Indicators	DCMP			HCMP			RCMP		
	EF <40%	EDS LV	EDV LV	EF >55%	EDS LV	EDV LV	EF >55%	EDS LV	EDV LV
Aral region	0,68	0,64	0,22	0,15	0,18	0,36	0,12	0,18	0,12
Maternal age > 35 years	0,56	0,53	0,32	0,26	0,24	0,32	0,06	0,12	0,32
Closely related marriage	0,44	0,48	0,30	0,24	0,19	0,28	0,12	0,06	0,05
Heredity	0,28	0,32	0,27	0,18	0,19	0,27	0,11	0,19	0,07
Preeclampsia	0,32	0,36	0,34	0,19	-0,21	0,32	0,19	-0,12	0,06
Polyhydramnios	0,25	0,28	0,27	0,18	0,22	0,36	0,18	0,14	0,06

As can be seen from Table 4, a similar trend of correlation relationships was noted with laboratory indicators. In children with DCMP, strong correlation relationship ($p < 0.001$) of such indicators as CPK-MB and NTpro BNP with the indicators of children living in the Aral Sea region ($r = 0.68$ and $r = 0.64$ –, respectively), as well as average correlation relationship ($p < 0.01$) with maternal age, closely related marriage and preeclampsia.

Thus, among the factors influencing the development of the disease, there are such as environmental, medical and biological factors, unfavorable maternal factors during pregnancy, past diseases. The presence of a chronic pathological process always has a significant impact on the physical development of children. But at the same time, it should be noted that the prescription of the disease also causes growth delay and development in children. In addition to obeying the laws, physical development depends on some factors of a socio-economic, biomedical, and environmental nature. Also, the study confirmed the presence of close pathogenetic relationships between indicators of structural and functional remodeling of the heart, endothelial function and the activity of neurohumoral mechanisms of progression of CHF, the severity of which is mainly due to health determinants.

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